

ANALYSIS OF THE INTEGRATED VISCOMETER CPB TO DETERMINE THE EFFICIENCY OF MEASURING THE DIFFERENCE OF NON-NEWTON LIQUID

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With the development of modern technology and industry, there is a growing demand for more complex analysis of fluids, and therefore liquids are studied in two types, and we study them as Newtonian and NonNewton fluids.

A fluid that does not obey the law of viscous friction is called a Newton. If we act on a non-Newtonian fluid with mechanical forces, we have a completely different effect. The viscosity of the liquid increases greatly and it begins to act almost like a solid. The bonding between fluid molecules increases with the force exerted on it, resulting in physical difficulties in moving such fluid layers[1]. The simplest pictorial everyday example of a non-Newtonian liquid is a mixture of starch with a small amount of water. The faster the external action of a suspended binder macromolecule in a liquid, the higher its viscosity [2].

In a non-Newtonian liquid, starch particles swell in water and physical bonds are formed between them in the form of randomly interconnected groups of molecules. We call such strong connections connections. With a sharp shock, these bonds do not allow the molecules to move, and the system is subject to external influences such as elastic leakage. With slow action, these bonds have some time to elongate and expand, and the network breaks down, and the molecules split evenly [3].

Thus, we distinguish between Newtonian and non-Newtonian fluids and consider the comparison of their main properties in table-1 below when conducting research on them.

Table 1. Comparative descriptions of the properties of liquids.

Character	Newtonian fluid (water)	Non-Newtonian fluid (thick and elastic substances)
Ability to harden when exposed	No	Yes
Readability	Yes	Yes (by mechanical action The non-Newton disappears into the liquid)
Viscosity	Little	Significantly under mechanical influence
Mixability	Easy	Diffuculty
Evaporation	Yes (evaporates, retains its properties when liquefied)	The water evaporates (turns into a mass similar to the same layer and loses its properties)
Freezing	Yes (turns to ice, retains its properties after melting from ice)	Yes (water freezes, starch rises from the bottom in the form of a frozen mass, retains its properties after thawing)

From the table above, we can see that many fluids exhibit non-Newtonian behavior. If the measured viscosity of a liquid depends on the shear rate at which the measurement is made, it is said to be non-Newtonian.

The viscosity is defined as the ratio of the shear stress to the shear rate when the fluid is subjected to the same shear, which is schematically shown in Fig-1.

Fig-1. The Newtonian fluid is the cut-off position between two parallel plates.

If the resistance force and the shear stress are proportional to the velocity of the bottom plate, that is, the shear rate, the fluid is called Newtonian. We see that its viscosity is proportional to the force of gravity. So the stickiness does not depend on how fast it moves; the cutting point simply increases to maintain the cutting speed. The greater the ratio of the shear stress to the shear rate, the higher the viscosity is represented by the two straight lines in Figure-2 below. The relationship between shear stress and shear rate in a non-Newtonian fluid can be varied and even time dependent. The constant viscosity coefficient for non-Newtonian fluids cannot be determined.

For fluid fluids, the concept of viscosity, which is commonly used in fluid mechanics to describe the shear properties of a fluid, is insufficient. Instead, they are best studied by several other rheological properties associated with voltage velocity tensors under different current conditions, which are measured with different instruments or rheometers. One type of non-Newtonian behavior that is typical for most fluids is a decrease in viscosity, measured by an increase in the sliding speed of the viscometer. This is called the thinning motion of the cut.

Fig- 2. The high viscosity is represented by two straight lines.

The ratio of the cutting thinner to the cutting speed starts at a high level, but decreases as the cutting speed increases. In Figure 2 above, the shear rate curve relative to the shear stress of the liquefaction fluid begins parallel to the high-viscosity fluid and ends parallel to the low-viscosity fluid. The liquid thins faster and it cuts faster.

Most fluids have a nonlinear relationship between shear stress and shear rate. This means that the measured viscometer depends on the type of viscometer used for the measurement, and we use SRV viscometer measurement. SRVs have a much higher shear rate than most rotary, capillary, and traction viscometers. Thus, SRV often exhibits a viscosity that is significantly different from that of a laboratory rotating instrument.

The following paragraphs affect linear measurements with typical cutting fluid measurements and Rheonics SRV.

Measuring the viscosity of cutting thinning materials. Concentrated detergent solutions, such as shampoos, dishwashing liquids, and fabric softeners, typically have a cutting-thinning property. When using a rotating viscometer such as a Brookfield DV to measure their viscosity, the viscosity decreases as the spindle speed increases, and it describes the thinning motion of the cut as shown in Fig-3.

Figure 3. Brookfield DV The viscosity indicated relative to the speed of a conventional rotary viscometer.

Although the cutting speed is not well defined for most viscometers, it can be shown that the cutting speed of vibrating viscometers such as Rheonics SRV is one hundred times faster than that of conventional Brookfield, Fann, or other rotating viscometers. This means that the SRV is working on the tail with a high shear on the shear rate curve. The viscosity it exhibits is much lower than other vibration measurement processes.

Alternatively, Rheonics SRV can be used as a sensor in the control chain to automatically adjust one or more process variables to keep product viscosity within specified limits. Typical application is used in flexo or rotogravure presses, where Rheonics SRV is used to maintain a constant ink viscosity.

It is important that SRV is not calculated based on static measurements. Placing the SRV in a motionless liquid beaker usually does not provide measurements that correspond to the measurements obtained in the actual process line at the flow rate specific to the operation of the process.

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